

tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine (~ 500 mg) which was finally purified by crystallisation from CHCl_3 –methanol as colourless needles *methyl 2-eno[2,3-*g*]tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine-olean-12-en-28-oate* (4), m.p 135–40° (Found C, 72.6; H, 8.45; N, 12.7. $\text{C}_{88}\text{H}_{47}\text{O}_2\text{N}_5$ requires: C, 72.66; H, 8.62; N, 12.84%); δ 8.67 (s, 5'-H), 8.21 (s, 6'-H), 5.3 (1H, t, 12-H), 3.65 (3H, s, COOMe) and 0.9–2.5 (21H, 7×Me); ν_{max} 2145 (N_5), 1720 (ester C=O), 1565, 1555, 1415 and 1380 cm^{-1} (characteristic of pyrimidine ring); *2-eno[2,3-*g*]tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine-lup-20(29)-ene* (5); m.p 165–70° (Found C, 76.5; H, 9.2; N, 13.8. $\text{C}_{82}\text{H}_{47}\text{N}_5$ requires C, 76.64; H, 9.36; N, 13.97%) δ 8.6 (s, 5'-H of tetrazolo form), 8.2 (s, 6'-H of azido form), 4.7 (2H, d, C=CH₂) and 0.9–2.5 (21H, 7×Me), ν_{max} 2140 (N_5), 1565, 1555, 1415 and 1380 cm^{-1} (characteristic of pyrimidine ring); *methyl-2-eno[2,3-*g*]tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine-lup-20(29)-en-28-oate* (6): m.p 135–40° (Found C, 72.6; H, 8.45; N, 12.7. $\text{C}_{88}\text{H}_{47}\text{O}_2\text{N}_5$ requires C, 72.66; H, 8.62; N, 12.84%); δ 8.67 (s, 5'-H of tetrazolo form), 8.2 (s, 6'-H of azido form), 4.7 (2H, d, C=CH₂), 3.65 (3H, s, COOMe) and 0.9–2.5 (18H, 6×Me); ν_{max} 2140 (N_5), 1720 cm^{-1} (methyl ester C=O), 1565, 1555, 1415 and 1380 cm^{-1} (characteristic of pyrimidine ring).

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Pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines. Synthesis and Reaction of 2-Amino-3-cyanopyrroles

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IMPORTANT antibiotics tubercidin¹, toyocamycin¹ and sangivamycin² have pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine moiety in their structures. 4-Amino/hydroxy-

pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines have been reported to possess analgesic, anti-inflammatory, CNS depressant, anticonvulsant and sedative activities^{3,4}. In the present paper, we report the synthesis of 4-amino-pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines and some new 2-amino-3-cyanopyrroles, important intermediates for various fused heterocycles.

(2-Bromo-1-arylalkylidene)propanedinitriles (1) when condensed with various aromatic amines under mild Gewald reaction condition⁵, 2-amino-3-cyanopyrroles (2) were obtained, which on heterocyclisation with formamide in DMF/HCOOH afforded 4-amino-5,7-disubstitutedpyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (3).

R = C_6H_5 , 4- $\text{OH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, 4- $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, 4- $\text{ClO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$,

R₁ = C_6H_5 , 4- $\text{OH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, 4- $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, 4- $\text{ClO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, 4- $\text{BrO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, 4- $\text{IO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$.

It was observed during the synthesis of 2-amino-1,4-disubstituted-3-cyanopyrroles (2) that the reaction was unsuccessful in the presence of a strong electron-releasing group such as NH_2 or OH and a strong electron-withdrawing NO_2 group in the 4-position of primary aromatic amines. Further, the reaction failed to yield the desired 2 when meta-substituted-aromatic amines were used.

Ir (KBr) spectra of 2-amino-3-cyanopyrroles (2) exhibited bands near 3400 and 3320 (NH_2), 2200 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) and 1600 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{C}$ ring), and 4-amino-5,7-disubstituted-7H-pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (3) showed bands near 3470, 3300 and 3100 cm^{-1} (NH_2), ~1640 (NH_2) and 1590–1480 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ ring). The absence of a strong band ~2200 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) was indicative of the completion of reaction between 2 and formamide.

Compounds 3g, h, j failed to show any anticancer activity when screened against Leukemia tumor at the doses of 60, 120 and 240 mg/kg.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin–Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. The purity of compounds were checked by tlc using silica gel-G and spots were visualised by exposing the dried plates to iodine vapours.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-AMINO-3-CYANOPYRROLES (2) AND 4-AMINOPYRROLO-[2,3-d]PYRIMIDINES (3)

Sl. no.	R ₁	Yield %	M p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					O	H	N
When R=C ₆ H ₅							
2a	2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	30	125	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃	78.98 (79.09)	5.72 (5.53)	15.50 (15.37)
2b	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	52	137	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃	79.23 (79.09)	5.08 (5.53)	15.58 (15.37)
2c	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	70	174-5	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃	69.28 (69.50)	4.27 (4.12)	14.37 (14.30)
2d	4-IC ₆ H ₄	50	223-5	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ IN ₃	58.19 (53.00)	3.00 (3.14)	11.13 (10.91)
When R=4-OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄							
2e	C ₆ H ₅	59	141-3	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃	78.92 (79.09)	5.41 (5.53)	15.62 (15.37)
2f	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	48	175-6	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	75.07 (75.23)	5.79 (5.65)	13.67 (13.85)
2g	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	41	157-8	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ClN ₃	70.27 (70.24)	4.48 (4.58)	13.52 (13.65)
2h	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	50	197-8	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ BrN ₃	61.09 (61.37)	4.21 (4.00)	11.99 (11.92)
2i	4-IC ₆ H ₄	46	224-5	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ IN ₃	54.27 (54.15)	3.45 (3.53)	10.61 (10.52)
When R=4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄							
2j	C ₆ H ₅	64	153-4	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	74.93 (74.72)	5.29 (5.23)	14.33 (14.52)
2k	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	40	199-200	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	75.39 (75.23)	5.77 (5.65)	13.57 (13.85)
2l	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60	181-2	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	71.36 (71.46)	5.37 (5.36)	13.29 (13.16)
2m	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	30	204-5	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O	66.94 (66.77)	4.75 (4.86)	12.77 (12.98)
2n	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	36	167-8	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ O	58.79 (58.71)	3.97 (3.83)	11.52 (11.41)
2o	4-IC ₆ H ₄	65	202-3	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ IN ₃ O	51.91 (52.07)	3.51 (3.40)	9.87 (10.12)
When R=4-ClC ₆ H ₄							
2p	C ₆ H ₅	76	174-5	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃	69.62 (69.50)	4.32 (4.12)	14.08 (14.30)
2q	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	45	182-3	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ClN ₃	70.87 (70.24)	4.34 (4.58)	13.88 (13.65)
2r	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	50	196-7	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O	66.89 (66.77)	4.21 (4.36)	13.09 (12.98)
2s	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	55	219-21	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃	62.37 (62.21)	3.12 (3.38)	12.94 (12.80)
2t	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	60	245-7	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ BrClN ₃	54.88 (54.79)	3.13 (2.98)	11.39 (11.28)
2u	4-IC ₆ H ₄	58	265-6	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ ClIN ₃	48.87 (48.66)	2.36 (2.64)	10.43 (10.01)
When R=4-OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄							
3a	C ₆ H ₅	61	177-8	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃	76.12 (75.98)	5.47 (5.37)	18.51 (18.65)
3b	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	64	198-9	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	72.87 (72.71)	5.61 (5.49)	17.20 (16.96)
3c ^a	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	76	224-6	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ClN ₃	67.90 (68.16)	4.36 (4.52)	16.47 (16.73)
3d	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	81	232-4	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ BrN ₃	60.92 (60.17)	3.93 (3.98)	14.25 (14.17)
3e	4-IC ₆ H ₄	84	214-6	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ IN ₃	53.58 (53.53)	3.67 (3.54)	13.30 (13.14)
When R=4-ClC ₆ H ₄							
3f	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	75	200-1	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ClN ₃	68.25 (68.16)	4.71 (4.52)	16.59 (16.73)
3g	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	70	224-6	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O	65.23 (65.05)	4.09 (4.31)	16.33 (15.97)
3h	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	96	266-9	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃	60.81 (60.86)	3.33 (3.41)	15.94 (15.77)
3i	4-IC ₆ H ₄	90	231-2	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ ClIN ₃	48.38 (48.40)	2.94 (2.71)	12.22 (12.54)

^aCompounds 2a-c, 2e-g, 2j-m and 2p-q crystallised from ethanol and all other 2 and 3 crystallised from ethanol-DMF mixture. ^bm/e 334 (M⁺), 333, 318, 307, 299, 292, 279, 271, 265, 257, 243.

2-Amino-1,4-disubstituted-3-cyanopyrroles (2): To the solution of (2-bromo-1-aryllalkylidene) propane-dinitrile (0.02 mol) in n-propanol (50 ml) was added primary aromatic amine (0.02 mol) dissolved in n-propanol (10 ml) portionwise with constant stirring at 60–5° over a period of 30 mins. After the completion of addition, reaction mixture was further stirred for 1 h at the same temperature and for 1 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was diluted with water (25 ml) and the solid separated was filtered, dried and crystallised (Table 1).

4-Amino-5, 7-disubstituted-7H-pyrrolo[2, 3-d]pyridines (3): A mixture of 2-amino-1,4-disubstituted-3-cyanopyrroles (2; 0.01 mol), formamide (15 ml), dimethylformamide (5 ml) and formic acid (2 ml) was refluxed for 6–8 h. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature and the solid obtained was filtered, washed with cold ethanol, dried and crystallised (Table 1).

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Flavonoids of the Flowers of *Ichnocarpus frutescence*

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ICHNOCARPUS frutescence R. Br. (Apocynaceae), a medicinally important large evergreen laticiferous woody creeper with rusty red appearance and ascending upto an altitude of 4000 ft, is found throughout India¹⁻³. A literature survey revealed that no investigation of its flavonoid constituents has been carried out. In this communication, we

report the isolation of a flavonol and a flavonol glycoside from the methanolic extract of the fresh flowers of *I. frutescence* and their characterisation as quercetin and quercetin-3-O-β-D-glucopyranoside, respectively.

The concentrated methanolic extract of fresh flowers of the plant, collected locally, was fractionated successively with (i) petroleum ether, (ii) ether, (iii) ethyl acetate, (iv) butan-1-ol and (v) aqueous butan-1-ol (1 : 4). Shinoda test revealed that only ethyl acetate extract contained the flavonoid. This fraction was then chromatographed over a silica gel column and two flavonoids (compounds A and B) were obtained.

Compound A: It was eluted by benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 2) and crystallised from acetone-methanol (1 : 1) as yellow crystals, m.p. 316°; R_f 0.64 (BuOH-AcOH-H₂O, 6 : 1 : 2); gave positive Shinoda test but negative Molisch test. It was identified as quercetin on the basis of colour reactions, its penta-acetate (m.p. 197–98°), spectral analysis, co-pc and m.p.

Compound B: Further elution of the column using the same solvent gave compound B, crystallised as yellow needle shaped clustres, m.p. 235–36° (Found: C, 54.39; H, 4.29. C₂₁H₂₀O₁₂ requires: C, 54.31; H, 4.31%); M^+ 464; R_f 0.58 (BuOH-AcOH-H₂O); gave olive-green colouration with FeCl₃; gave orange-red Shinoda test and positive Molisch test; the dull brown coloration with uv, changed to bright yellow when exposed to uv/NH₃; λ_{max} 254, 370 (MeOH), 269, 417 (+NaOMe), 276, 388 (+NaOAc), 260, 385 (+NaOAc/H₂BO₃), 272, 438 (+AlCl₃), 268, 405 nm (+AlCl₃/HCl). λ_{max} 254 and 370 nm indicated the compound B to be a flavonol glycoside. On acid hydrolysis it gave an aglycone, m.p. 315.5°, identified as quercetin. The sugar was identified as D-glucose by co-tlc⁴. The aglycone-sugar ratio⁵ was found to be 1 : 1, suggesting compound B to be a monoglucoside of quercetin. A bathochromic shift of 68 nm in band-I absorption with AlCl₃ indicated the sugar linkage at 3-position⁶. Periodate oxidation and formic acid estimation suggested the pyranose form of D-glucose⁷. The pmr spectra of the glucoside acetate, in addition to typical signals for quercetin skeleton exhibited seven glucosyl protons (δ -ppm 5.61–3.82). Hydrolysability of the glucoside with almond emulsin showed β -linkage⁸. Thus compound B was characterised as quercetin-3-O-β-D-glucopyranoside.

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